

Electrometric Titrations with Two Polarisable Electrodes : Use of Platinum-Graphite Bi-Electrode System in Iodine Estimation

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Applicability of polarisable Platinum-Graphite bi-electrode system has been studied for the electro-metric estimation of iodine with sodium thiosulphate. Well defined breaks in the current volume curves indicative of sharp end-points are obtained. Variations in the applied potential in the range 20–200 mV. and that in the concentration of iodine in the range $3.6 \times 10^{-2}M$ to $7.2 \times 10^{-4}M$ have been studied. It is found that graphite used as positive electrode suits better.

Use of two polarisable indicator electrodes has been made in several redox estimations because of the improved sensitivity¹; several bi-electrode systems have been employed^{2,3}. The applicability of graphite electrode in combination with platinum, when polarised, is now shown for the determination of iodine in dilute solutions. The utility of graphite electrode as anode and as cathode, the effect of variation in the applied potential and the optimum concentration range of iodine that can be estimated with accuracy have also been studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

The electrode system consisted of a platinum micro electrode and a graphite electrode prepared with a little manganese dioxide as described earlier⁴; the latter electrode was impregnated with molten wax and the tip was scratched before use, to yield the desired results⁵. The electrode assembly was fitted in a rubber stopper having necessary holes for nitrogen inlet and for burette tip; the inter electrode distance being 3–4 cms. The electrodes were cleaned before every run and always kept in distilled water when not in use. The applied e.m.f. was obtained from a battery-operated potentiometer; the current through the cell and a series resistance (6600 Ω) was measured with a sensitive galvanometer, which was provided with series and parallel resistances for critical damping.

The necessary chemicals used were B.D.H.A.R. grade, except when mentioned and all solutions were prepared in double distilled water. The stock solution of iodine was prepared and stored as described by Vogel⁶. It was standardised with sodium thiosulphate solution (prepared from extra pure E. Merck reagent), the strength of which was also simultaneously determined potentiometrically daily before use, with a standard potassium dichromate solution.

1. K. Stulik and F. Vydra, "Chelates in Analytical Chemistry", Vol. 2, M. Decker, Inc., New York, 1969, 102.
2. *Ibid.*, 101.
3. J. T. Stock, *Anal. Chem.*, 1964, **36**(5), 358R; 1966, **38**(5), 452R; 1968, **40**(5), 396R.
4. B. B. Prasad, D. Singh and B. N. Prasad, *J. Sci. Res., B.H.U.*, 1959-60, **X** (1), 73.
5. P. J. Elving and D. L. Smith, *Anal. Chem.*, 1960, **32**(13), 1849.
6. A. I. Vogel, "Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longman Green and Co., London, 1962, 355.

A known amount of iodine solution was placed into the titration cell and to it an appropriate amount of water was added to adjust the total volume to about 30 ml. The standard thio. solution was administered from a 5 ml semi-micro burette with 0.01 ml divisions and the solution was stirred uniformly during the titration using a magnetic stirrer. Galvanometer readings were taken at regular intervals (usually two minutes) after each addition of the titrant. Experiments were repeated at least three times to confirm the reproducibility of the end-point.

With the above arrangements the following two series of experiments were carried out. In the first, with a constant amount of iodine (61.13 mg) titrations were performed using graphite electrode, anodically polarised with respect to platinum and in the second series, this polarisation was reversed. With different constant polarising potentials (varied in the range 20–200 mV) the galvanometer readings over the entire titration range for the end-point were recorded; the results are returned graphically in fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Current-volume curves for titration of iodine (61.13 mg) at various applied e.m.f.

Keeping the polarising potential constant, different amounts of iodine were next titrated in both the two different arrangements *i.e.*, (a) when graphite electrode was positive and (b) when platinum electrode was positive. Fig. 2 shows the nature of the titration curves obtained for various amounts of iodine at 100 mV constant polarising e.m.f.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The estimations recorded in table 1 show the suitability of this platinum-graphite bi-electrode system for the determination of iodine. Curves in Fig. 1 and 2 being typical of several experiments give breaks indicative of sharp end-points. The magnitude of current

during titration shows initially a slow decrease followed by a larger decrease near the end-point and beyond which it either becomes constant or shows a very slight change. However, this slight diminution does not obstruct in any way the location of the end-point. It

Fig. 2. Current-volume curves for titration of iodine at constant applied e.m.f. (100 mV).

is noted here that though the breaks in both the cases are distinct, that with graphite as positive appears to be better suited thus confirming the suitability for such determinations. Similar are the results obtained with graphite rods impregnated with wax, for anodic processes at positive potentials where DME is unable to function⁷.

TABLE 1

Approximate Concn. of Iodine solution	Actual amount in mg.		Percent Error
	Taken	Found	
$7.2 \times 10^{-4}M$	5.50	5.44	1.09
$2.2 \times 10^{-3}M$	17.03	16.94	0.52
3.7 „ „	28.34	28.13	0.74
5.3 „ „	41.05	40.62	1.04
8.0 „ „	61.13	60.85	0.45
9.2 „ „	70.85	70.77	0.11
$1.5 \times 10^{-2}M$	119.10	119.10	0.00
2.6 „ „	199.75	199.75	0.00
3.6 „ „	274.50	274.50	0.00

7. P. Kabaskalian and M. D. Yudis, "Snell-Hilton, Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemical Analysis", Vol. 3, 196.

The use of polarisable electrodes helps the attainment of equilibrium sooner, even in those cases where the electrode is known to be "slow". Because of a low current there is a small reduction at one of the electrodes. The resulting decrease in concentration is compensated by a corresponding oxidation at the other electrode. The influence of an increase in the applied potential (varied in the range 20–200 mV) is mainly to increase the current in the pre-equivalence stage without affecting the end-point.

The method is simple, quick and avoids much of instrumentation. It may be used for détermination in dilute solutions to yield reliable results for iodine estimations in aqueous potassium iodide solutions. In presence of acid or small amounts of other ions, the current in the post equivalence region sometimes shows an increase depending on the nature of ions present (curves not shown here). The applicability in such cases too remains unimpaired.

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